

Extended Reality simulator to evaluate remote control interactions for reach stackers

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Introduction

Remote control of off-highway machinery systems can bring many benefits to companies and operators. Managers don't need to handle personnel relocations, and operations time is optimized as an operator doesn't have to move from one machine to another, as they can seamlessly switch to control another machine from the same workstation. Operators could also benefit from better ergonomics, less noisy environments, and the risk for injuries would also be significantly reduced. Remote control would also allow to delegate some easier tasks, such as driving towards a specified location, to an automated system, and operators can intervene only for more delicate processes.

That said, remote control does not come without some caveats. An operator's situational awareness risks being considerably reduced, especially when they can only rely on traditional camera feeds with a limited field of view and that can only capture bidimensional information. It is also hard to perceive other important environmental things such as wind strength and direction and outdoor temperature (to know, for example if the ground might be slippery).

The proposed simulator allows for a user-centric approach (Helin et al., 2024) to the interaction and system design, and it was used to reach an acceptable usability level in terms of features and functionality before starting the implementation of the real remote-control prototype (see Figure D. 4). This abstract describes the final simulator and features, and it outlines the key results that were taken and considered for the actual prototype.

Figure D. 4. The simulator application running on VTT's Powerwall.

Remote reach stacker simulator for User-Centric Design

To simulate a realistic scenario and obtain usability results from the users, they were asked to use the simulator to (i) pick up a container on the harbor's ground by aligning the reach stacker's spreader to it and then locking the twist locks into the container's corner castings; (ii) release the container on a truck's flatbed. They had no time limits, and they didn't have to use all the functionalities but only the ones that were deemed useful (an initial tutorial would still showcase all the possibilities offered by the simulator).

Hardware description

The application was developed to run on VTT's wall-sized Powerwall display, as well as on a traditional FullHD monitor. The UI was adapted for these two cases, but apart from that the application was the same one. Unity 2022.3 LTS was chosen as for the game engine, while a Logitech Extreme 3D joystick and an Ultraleap IR 170 hand-tracking sensors were used as input devices (together with mouse and keyboard). The application was tested on Windows 11 operating system.

Visualization

The application is based on four 360° camera streams. The cameras are placed in key locations that were determined in previous studies (Alesani, 2023), namely one front camera placed in what is now the operator cabin in real reach stackers; a second camera is placed on top of the spreader, to allow for visibility behind a grabbed container and to have a "top view" when trying to align the spreader's twist locks to a container's corner castings; a third camera is placed in the back of the reach stacker, mostly for safety reasons; the fourth camera shows a "drone view" that allows for a third-person perspective on the reach stacker and its surroundings (see Figure D. 5). Camera views are highly customizable: users can dock them to the bottom of the screen, choose which one to have as main camera, and place them around the Powerwall display as "picture-in-picture" views that can be resized and customized with, for example, different fields of view.

Figure D. 5. Camera system's preview images and their docking positions.

Even with multiple views, it might still be hard to have a precise sense of perspective when trying to lock a container or releasing it on a truck's flatbed. UI indicators and AR hints were developed to enhance the user's situational awareness and performance for this type of task.

Figure D. 6. AR guidance system elements: (a), (b) - vehicle path and pick up/placement locations; (c), (d) - twist lock/corner casting positions, center line, and tipping axis; (e) - counterweight safety area and obstacle tracking; (f) - load chart, centre of mass

While many of the AR visuals are always available (like the ones seen above), some others are context-dependent and are only visible during a specific part of the task the user is performing, for example when locking the container (see Figure D. 7).

Figure D. 7. When the user has to lock a container, color-coded AR lines appear to indicate the proper alignment between twist locks and corner castings (on the left). Another experimental feature is a real-time LiDAR scan of the container that shows a 3D rotatable

Interactions

The Logitech Extreme 3D joystick was used to simulate a real reach stacker joystick, and the mapping of the controls was kept as close as possible to the one in the real vehicles (see Figure 5). Tilting the stick forward and backward makes the reach stacker's boom rotate respectively downward and upward, while tilting it left and right would makes the telescopic part of the boom respectively retract and extend. Buttons on top of the joystick are used to control the reach stacker's spreader, which can rotate clockwise or counterclockwise parallel to the ground, or shift left and right along the turntable the connects it to the boom (a real spreader has some additional controls that were not considered for the simulator).

Figure D. 8. The user aligns the spreader's twist locks to the container's corner castings by controlling the joystick.

Ultraleap's IR 170 hand-tracking sensor is used to track a few gestures that were made available to the user. Hand gestures only affect visualization aspects of the application, and have no effect in the

simulated real-world, remote-controlled environment. They are only tracked for the left hand, as the right one is supposed to handle the joystick and might produce undesired gestures when controlling the reach stacker. There are two types of gestures. When a hand swipe is recognized, the main view switches camera feed either to the next one (if swiping from right to left) or to the previous one (if swiping from left to right). When the user performs a pinch with their thumb and index finger, the swipe gesture recognition is disabled, and they become able to “pan” the view on the screen around the 360° camera footage by moving the hand up, down, left or right (see Figure D. 9).

Figure D. 9. The user can “pan” through the 360° view by pinching the fingers and moving the hand up, down, left or right. An AR hint is shown on the bottom of the screen which visualizes the current tracking status (orange for no hands tracked, yellow for hand recognized but out of bounds, green hand available for gestures). Vertical arrows appear when the pinch gesture is active, and horizontal arrows show when the user can activate the swipe gesture.

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Appendix

Video of the final prototype: <https://youtu.be/gfgrw0SgZeM?si=H-YwZ16ZCszbddXC>

